

Change in today's worldview

1. **Salimov Bakhriddin Lutfullaevich.** Professor of Tashkent State Transport University.
2. **Aloev Shuhrathoja Shavkatovich.** Student of Tashkent State Transport University.

Abstract

In the article, it is philosophical that no one can correctly say what will happen tomorrow, from which direction the danger will come, the world surrounding us today is becoming extremely complex and will remain so in the near future, therefore the issue of maintaining the path of sustainable development will always be relevant for the nations. analyzed in terms of

Key words: world, country, risks, uncertainty, purpose, stability.

INTRODUCTION

What is liveliness? What is the meaning of life? Questions about the purpose of human life have been tormenting mankind for thousands of years. Answers to such questions by the representatives of mankind, who are considered the most perfect among creatures, have been presented in different contexts in different periods, but the relevance of these questions has not lost its importance even today¹. After all, a person who is considered a conscious being while living in this world looks for meaning in his life, gets confused by the complicated situations that arise in his life and tries to find a solution to them. Sometimes he finds answers to his questions, sometimes he struggles to find answers.

¹ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

MAIN PART

In fact, it is difficult to find a hundred percent answer to questions of this content. Just as the socio-economic, political-legal, cultural-educational conditions of the societies that existed in different eras are different, the ways of life of the people who have lived to this day and are still living their lives have never been the same and will never be the same². It follows from this that it is natural that every society, every person has different views on life and answers to the questions that arise in this regard. However, it should be recognized that the situations in some societies and the lifestyles of some people may be partially similar. Then their conclusions about life will be compatible with each other. Then there will be opportunities to learn from the lives of others and avoid the mistakes and shortcomings they have made³. As we mentioned above, these aspects are also relevant to societies, states, in particular, to the fate of Uzbekistan. After all, how will the 21st century come to the people of Uzbekistan? How much better will people's lives be than yesterday? Do we realize that the path of reform and renewal that we have chosen for ourselves is a very difficult one? Do we have a clear enough idea of what problems, difficulties, trials we may face on this path? these thoughts should never leave us. We think that then our future will be great. Therefore, "at the same time, a deep analysis of the development path of our country, today's world market situation has changed dramatically, and the competition is becoming stronger in the conditions of globalization, which requires the development and implementation of a completely new approach and principles for the development of our country at a more stable and rapid pace⁴.

² Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). Жизненный путь природы и общества состоит из цепи случайностей и необходимостей. *Colloquium-journal*, (24 (76)), 55-57.

³ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

⁴ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг фармони “Ўзбекистон Республикасини янада ривожлантириш

The situation shows that not everyone can correctly understand what will happen tomorrow, from which direction the danger will come. The world that surrounds us today is extremely complex and will remain so in the near future. Sustainability cannot be maintained simply by being aware of those risks, simply assessing them⁵. So, what should be done?! The following points can be given as a correct answer to this question: "It seems that it is not enough to be able to relate to the emerging threats to security and stability today. We need to understand the nature of the dangers that exist. We need to determine their sources and interactions in time." We need to determine the conditions for maintaining stability in society and use them effectively. The stable and steady development of the Republic of Uzbekistan depends on them. In fact, the maintenance of peace and tranquility is very important for Uzbekistan, which has chosen its own independent development path and is now becoming more and more stable in terms of market relations, and all kinds of unexpected calamities and instability caused by them pose an equally great danger. After all, a society and a state that is moving from one system to a completely new system can be brought to the brink of destruction even by unexpected imbalances⁶. Therefore, it is necessary to work with extreme caution in this area. The transition from the administrative command style of centralized planning and management to the market economy is not the renewal or improvement of the existing way of doing business, but the introduction of a completely new way of doing business. It is a transition from one state of quality to another. This is a completely new philosophy of life for people. Accordingly, it cannot be implemented as a one-time event, but requires a long period of time,

бўйича Ҳаракатлар стратегияси тўғрисида". Халқ сўзи. 2017 йил, 8-феврал

⁵ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

⁶ Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). Жизненный путь природы и общества состоит из цепи случайностей и необходимостей. Colloquium-journal, (24 (76)), 55-57.

including several stages.

CONCLUSION

Now, together with material needs, people also have spiritual needs, without which it is difficult to imagine our life today. In particular, a person's desire to know his identity is considered one of these needs. In fact, every person who has a certain level of intelligence and understanding should strive to know who he is, choose his own life path, and if necessary, try to build a "Free and Prosperous Homeland, a free and prosperous life" for himself. If every compatriot living in independent Uzbekistan thinks about these things, if he thinks about them, not only these but also other questions, problems and goals should always be in the center of our attention. Inculcating the above-mentioned philosophy of life into the consciousness of our people should first of all be one of the main tasks of social and humanitarian sciences, especially philosophy, sociology, national idea, and the foundations of spirituality.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг фармони “Ўзбекистон Республикасини янада ривожлантириш бўйича Ҳаракатлар стратегияси тўғрисида”. Халқ сўзи. 2017 йил, 8-феврал. 119 б.
2. Салимов Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич (2020). Жизненный путь природы и общества состоит из цепи случайностей и необходимостей. *Colloquium-journal*, (24 (76)), 55-57.
3. Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.